

Kinetics and Mechanism of Anation of Aquachromium(III) Ions by L-Cysteine

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Elucidation of mechanism of anation of aquachromium(III) ions by amino acids has been the subject of several investigations¹⁻¹⁶. Apart from some discrepancies regarding the rate dependence on $[\text{ligand}]_T$ ¹³, a general pattern of the mechanism given is an ion-pair interchange type. However, the intimate mechanism—the process of interchange of the outer-sphere ligand into the available inner-sphere—is still controversial¹⁻¹⁶.

The present work reports the kinetic study of aquachromium(III) anation by L-cysteine. L-Cysteine, a sulphur containing amino acid, has three coordinating centres viz. N, O and S (pK values: 10.78, 1.71 and 8.33, respectively) and its reaction with aquachromium(III) has not been studied so far. Also, GTF¹⁷ (a low-molecular-weight chromium(III) complex), reported to possess insulin potentiating activity, contains cysteine as one of the constituents.

Results and Discussion

It is found that k_{obs} is a function of $[\text{cysteine}]_T$ (4.0×10^{-2} to 16.0×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³), $[\text{H}^+]$ (2.9×10^{-4} to 18.2×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³), μ (0.3–1.0 mol dm⁻³), EtOH (0–25%, v/v) and T (35–50°) (Table 1). As $[\text{cysteine}]_T$ increases, k_{obs} increases but not nearly in direct proportions and appears to reach a limiting value at higher $[\text{cysteine}]_T$ indicating existence of an ion-pair equilibrium between the reactants¹⁸.

In the anation reactions of aquachromium(III) ions by other ligands, it was suggested that increase of rate constants at lower $[\text{H}^+]$ is due to the conjugate base formation¹⁹. Increase in pH increases the hydroxo-species concentration (which has a

proven labilising effect) and hence the rate is increased. The water-exchange rate constant of penta-aquahydroxochromium(III) is 100 times higher than that of hexaaquachromium(III)²⁰.

Ion-pairing between positively charged species $[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+}/[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5\text{OH}]^{2+}$ and H_3A^+ is not possible and, therefore, our observations lead to suggest that $[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+}/[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5\text{OH}]^{2+}$ and H_2A are the reactive species. The following scheme and reaction sequence are, therefore, proposed to explain the rate-variations with $[\text{H}^+]$ and $[\text{cysteine}]_T$ (coordinated waters are omitted for brevity).

(A = cys⁻).

Reaction sequence :

TABLE 1—VALUES OF k_{obs} FOR ANATION OF AQUACHROMIUM(III) IONS BY L-CYSTEINE HYDROCHLORIDE

$10^4[H^+]$ mol dm ⁻³	μ mol dm ⁻³	$10^3[Cr^{III}]_T$ mol dm ⁻³	% EtOH (v/v)	$10^2[cysteine]_T$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^4 k_{obs} s^{-1}$			
					35°	40°	45°	50°
18.2	1.0	4.0	0	4.0	0.14	0.26	0.36	0.46
				8.0	0.25	0.46	0.61	0.79
				12.0	0.34	0.60	0.81	1.06
				16.0	0.42	0.70	0.92	1.22
11.5	0.3 0.5 0.7 0.9 1.0	3.0 4.0	10 15 20 25	4.0	0.17	0.30	0.44	0.57
				8.0	0.30	0.50	0.75	0.97
				12.0	0.40	0.66	0.99	1.19
				16.0	0.48	0.79	1.14	1.43
				4.0			0.35	
							0.38	
							0.40	
							0.43	
							0.44	
							0.32	
7.2			0	4.0	0.21	0.34	0.55	0.70
				8.0	0.36	0.57	0.86	1.14
				12.0	0.48	0.74	1.12	1.43
				16.0	0.57	0.88	1.31	1.67
4.6				4.0	0.27	0.43	0.67	0.89
				8.0	0.46	0.70	1.04	1.35
				12.0	0.57	0.85	1.28	1.61
				16.0	0.67	1.00	1.51	1.89
2.9				4.0	0.29	0.49	0.85	1.25
				8.0	0.50	0.85	1.39	2.01
				12.0	0.65	1.09	1.72	2.50
				16.0	0.79	1.31	2.08	2.86

The above mechanism was tested by plotting k_{obs}^{-1} against $[cysteine]_T^{-1}$ which yielded straight lines (Fig. 1). At $[H^+] \geq 4.6 \times 10^{-4}$ mol dm⁻³, the straight lines converge to a constant intercept, and thus become independent of $[H^+]$ below pH 3.6. In this low pH range, $K_a K_h K_{OS2}$ and $k_2 K_a K_h K_{OS2}$ can be neglected in comparison to $K_a K_{OS1} [H^+]$ and $k_1 K_a K_{OS1} [H^+]$, respectively, and also $[H^+] K_h$ and $K_a K_h$ as compared to $[H^+]^2 + [H^+] K_a$. The equation (2) then simplifies to equation (3),

$$k_{obs}^{-1} = \frac{1}{k_1} + \frac{[H^+] + K_a}{k_1 K_a K_{OS1}} [cysteine]_T \quad (3)$$

Plots producing straight lines according to

By appropriate substitution, the above mechanism leads to rate equation (1),

$$k_{obs} = \frac{(k_1 K_a K_{OS1} [H^+] + k_2 K_a K_h K_{OS2}) [cysteine]_T}{[H^+]^2 + [H^+] K_a + [H^+] K_h + K_a K_h + (K_a K_{OS1} [H^+] + K_a K_h K_{OS2}) [cysteine]_T} \quad (1)$$

whose reciprocal is

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{1}{k_{obs}} &= \frac{K_a K_{OS1} [H^+] + K_a K_h K_{OS2}}{k_1 K_a + K_{OS1} [H^+] + k_2 K_a K_h K_{OS2}} \\
 &+ \frac{[H^+]^2 + [H^+] K_a + [H^+] K_h + K_a K_h}{k_1 K_a K_{OS1} [H^+] + k_2 K_a K_h K_{OS2}} \cdot \frac{1}{[cysteine]_T} \quad (2)
 \end{aligned}$$

TABLE 2—VALUES OF ANATION AND OUTER-SPHERE ASSOCIATION CONSTANTS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Temp. °C	$[Cr^{II}]_T = 4.0 \times 10^3$ mol dm ⁻³ , $\mu = 1.0$ mol dm ⁻³ (KNO ₃)			
	$10^4 k_1$ s ⁻¹	$10^3 k_2$ s ⁻¹	K_{OS1} mol ⁻¹ dm ³	K_{OS2} mol ⁻¹ dm ³
25	—	—	—	1.10 ^a
35	1.28	0.35	9.09	8.70
37	—	—	—	1.10 ^b
40	1.75	0.39	6.86	5.99
45	2.22	0.45	5.41	4.83
50	2.77	0.57	10.89	9.69
			$\bar{K}_{OS1} = 8.06$	$\bar{K}_{OS2} = 7.30$

^aRef. 24. ^bRef. 25. ^cRef. 26.

TABLE 3—COMPARISON OF RATE CONSTANTS FOR ANATION OF $[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+}$ (k_1) AND $[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5\text{OH}]^{2+}$ (k_2) AND OF ACTIVATION PARAMETERS*

Ligand X	$k_1(\text{s}^{-1})$	ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	$k_1(\text{s}^{-1})$	ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
H ₂ O ^a	$10.5 \times 10^{-6}(k_{\text{ex}})$	108.6	+11.6	$0.76 \times 10^{-3}(k'_{\text{ex}})$	111.0	+55.6
DL- α -Alanine ^b	0.6×10^{-4}	64.9	-113.6	$0.46 \times 10^{-3}(45^\circ)$	77.0	-68.0
DL-Alanine ^c	—	—	—	0.40×10^{-3}	34.0	-201.7
DL-Serine ^d	0.6×10^{-4}	78.0	-72.5	—	—	—
L-Hydroxyproline ^e	$1.0 \times 10^{-4}(40^\circ)$	72.9	-98.2	$0.21 \times 10^{-3}(40^\circ)$	63.2	-114.1
DL-Tryptophan ^f	$1.2 \times 10^{-4}(40^\circ)$	65.6	-112.4	$0.25 \times 10^{-3}(40^\circ)$	85.0	-44.8
L-Cysteine ^g	1.3×10^{-4}	39.7	-190.7	0.35×10^{-3}	23.9	-214.0
Nitrilotriacetic acid ^h	1.7×10^{-4}	86.4	-36.8	—	—	—
L-Glutamine ⁱ	$1.8 \times 10^{-4}(40^\circ)$	52.0	-150.6	$0.46 \times 10^{-3}(40^\circ)$	43.7	-161.1
L-Phenylalanine/ DL-Phenylalanine ^k	1.9×10^{-4}	53.6	-141.7	$0.70 \times 10^{-3}(45^\circ)$	—	—
DL-Valine ^l	—	—	—	0.30×10^{-3}	53.9	-135.9
DL-Valine ⁱ	2.4×10^{-4}	90.4	-21.0	—	—	—
Glycine ^m	3.3×10^{-4}	58.0	-129.2	—	—	—
Sarcosine ⁿ	$3.6 \times 10^{-4}(40^\circ)$	54.7	-136.6	$1.23 \times 10^{-3}(50^\circ)$	—	—
Anthranilic acid ^o	4.7×10^{-4}	94.9	-0.6	—	—	—
Glycine ^p	6.8×10^{-4}	51.9	-42.7	—	—	—
Salicylic acid ^q	10.3×10^{-4}	74.5	-60.5	—	—	—

*All values at $\mu=1.0$ mol dm⁻³ and 35° except otherwise stated.

^aRef. 20 ; $\mu=0.7$ mol dm⁻³. ^bRef. 5 ; k_1 values obtained by extrapolation. ^cRef. 14 ; $\mu=0.03$ mol dm⁻³. ^dRef. 3 ; k_1 values obtained by extrapolation. ^eRef. 8. ^fRef. 12. ^gPresent work. ^hRef. 27 ; $\mu=0.25$ mol dm⁻³, water+30% EtOH. ⁱRef. 28. ^jRef. 9. ^kRef. 16 ; $\mu=0.0075$ mol dm⁻³. ^lRef. 4. ^mRef. 2 ; k_1 values obtained by extrapolation. ⁿRef. 10. ^oRef. 29 ; $\mu=0.1$ mol dm⁻³, water+50% EtOH. ^pRef. 1. ^qRef. 30.

Fig. 1. k_{obs}^{-1} vs $[\text{cysteine}]_T^{-1}$ plots ; $[\text{Cr}(\text{III})]_T = 4.0 \times 10^{-8}$ mol dm⁻³, $\mu = 1.0$ mol dm⁻³ (KNO₃).

equations (2) and (3) were used to calculate the values of k_1 , k_2 , K_{OS1} and K_{OS2} (Table 2). The activation enthalpy and entropy were calculated by Eyring equation (Table 3).

Distinction of an I_a from an I_d mechanism for anation reactions has been made on the basis of well established method of comparing the span of rate constant values for a variety of entering groups, X^{21,22}. But, instead of second order rate constants k ($=k_1K_{\text{OS1}}$ or k_2K_{OS2}), which has been used by most of the workers for this purpose, comparisons among first order rate constants are more reliable as K_{OS1} (and K_{OS2}) is dependent both on the charge and the nature of X. Table 3 records the first order anation rate constants of chromium(III) by a series of ligands. The range of the rates spanned by $[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+}$ is much larger than that spanned by $[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5\text{OH}]^{2+}$. Accordingly, the mechanisms assigned are I_a to the k_1 route and I_d to the k_2 route²¹. This is further supported by (i) the lower enthalpy of activation for anation than for water exchange²⁰ (Table 3) and (ii) the isokinetic plots (Fig. 2) for the anation of aquachromium(III) ions with various aminocarboxylic acid ligands.

The values of k_{obs} obtained in ethanol-water mixtures increase with increasing % EtOH (v/v). According to the Bjerrum equation¹⁹, K_{OS1} and K_{OS2} should increase with decrease in the dielectric constant of the medium and therefore, outer-sphere complexations are enhanced with a consequent increase in the rate. A plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/D$ was found to be linear, which shows that the simple electrostatic theory is applicable in the present case where the reacting zwitterion is regarded behaving as a 1 : 1 electrolyte having a—1 charge on the reaction site²³.

The slight increase in the observed rate constant with increase in ionic concentration (Table 1) indicates the easy removal of coordinated water molecule from the ion-pair.

Fig. 2. Isokinetic relationship, ΔH^\ddagger vs ΔS^\ddagger , for aminocarboxylic acid anations of $[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+}$ (A) and (B) $[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5\text{OH}]^{3+}$.

Experimental

L-Cysteine hydrochloride (chromatographically homogeneous, SRL) was used as such. Other chemicals were of reagent grade. The solutions were made in double-distilled air-free water. Stock solution of chromium nitrate was standardised by passing aliquots through an ion-exchange column of Dowex 50W-X8 (H-form) and titrating the effluent with standard NaOH (0.05 mol dm^{-3}) to phenolphthalein end-point.

An Elico LI-120 pH meter and a Bausch and Lomb Spectronic-20 spectrophotometer were used.

Kinetic measurements: All the kinetic measurements were made at 545 nm under pseudo-first order conditions of $[\text{cysteine}]_T \geq 10 [\text{Cr}^{III}]_T$. The first order plots were linear for at least three half-lives. k_{obs} values were obtained by linear least-squares regression analysis of the data from a computer base program (executed on a VAX 11/780 computer). Other details of the procedure are described elsewhere¹².

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